

THE FUTURE OF ARCTIC COASTAL ECOSYSTEMS

IDENTIFYING TRANSITIONS IN FJORD SYSTEMS AND ADJACENT COASTAL AREAS

Enable adaptive co-management of social-ecological fjord systems in the Arctic in the face of rapid cryosphere and biodiversity changes

RESEARCH TOPICS

1. Key drivers & data management
2. Biodiversity changes
3. Ecosystem function changes
4. Food provision & livelihoods
5. Nature-based tourism
6. Transdisciplinary synthesis
7. Policy dialogue & outreach

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